

The Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

*a non-profit
research institute affiliated with
the University of Bergen*

*Thormøhlensgate 47,
N-5006 Bergen
Norway*

NERSC Technical Report no. 290

MARCOAST
SERVICE UTILITY REPORT:
WATER QUALITY MONITORING OF THE NORTH SEA,
KATTEGAT AND SKAGERRAK
AND
HAB DETECTION, ALERT AND FORECASTING FOR
NORWEGIAN WATERS

by

**Lasse Pettersson, Anton Korosov, Kjell Maroni (FHL),
Gunnar S. Larsen (FD), Geir Johnsen (NTNU),
Bruce Hacket (met.no) and Karl Tangen (SINTEF)**

Bergen, October 22nd 2007

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

Thormøhlensgate 47

N-5006 Bergen - NORWAY

Phone: +47 55 20 58 00 Fax. +47 55 20 58 01

E-mail: administrasjon@nersc.noWeb.site: <http://www.nersc.no>

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REPORT

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MARINE AND COASTAL ENVIRONMENTAL INFORMATION SERVICES

MarCoast Service Utility Report:
***WP3350: Water quality monitoring of the North Sea,
Kattegat and Skagerrak***
and
***WP3430: HAB detection, alert and forecasting for
Norwegian waters***

	Name	Responsibility
Prepared by	Lasse H. Pettersson	WP leader
Contributions from	Kjell Maroni, FHL Gunnar Larsen, FD Geir Johnsen, NTNU Bruce Hacket, met.no Karl Tangen, SINTEF Aquaculture	SLA and other users
Review by		
Approved by		

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Abstract
<p>Seafood is the third largest export industry in Norway and fisheries and aquaculture accounts for 5% of the national export. Aquaculture is an important business in our rural coastal areas. Accordingly, for Norway it is essential to have an efficient early warning and monitoring system for harmful algae blooms in order to implement mitigation actions and saving values and the environment.</p> <p>Through the nine years “history” of the “<i>Water quality monitoring of the North Sea, Kattegat and Skagerrak</i>” service provided by Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Centre service for Norwegian waters implies the build up of a strong relation and confidence between the users and the provider. Both the technical skill in producing the information products, their presentation and dissemination as well as the regional knowledge in order to produce the correct assessment of the state of the environment are important service elements.</p> <p>The data provide by the NERSC MarCoast service is assessed <u>daily</u> by its users through the web-access the updated information products (http://HAB.nersc.no). The value of the service is first full materialized when a harmful algae bloom occurs and is early detected and that actions can be implemented according to contingency plan of the authorities and by the industry itself. During the regular monitoring mode the direct benefit is less visible, however a continuous monitoring is required by the authorities and expected by the industry.</p> <p>The natural variability of algae blooms during early spring to fall 2007 were monitored daily. No major harmful blooms causing significant losses to the Norwegian aquaculture industry were detected during Phase 2 of the project. At least three periods of alert algae bloom situations/events have been identified and notified to the aquaculture authorities (Directorate of Fisheries - FD) and to the industry (Norwegian Seafood Federation - FHL) through posting messages at the web-site and via direct mail to 50 core users. However, neither of these blooms reached the Norwegian coastal waters, or caused any major problems to Norwegian aquaculture sites. One local bloom in a fjord caused recently the attention of our users and the loss of 135 tons of salmon.</p>

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SCOPE

This document is the Service Utility Report for the “*Water quality monitoring of the North Sea, Kattegat and Skagerrak*” Service provided by Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC) to The Norwegian Directorate for Fisheries (FD) and The Norwegian Seafood Federation (FHL) in the framework of the GMES MARCOAST project Work Package 3350 - Phase 2. It corresponds to deliverable U7 as defined in the ESA Statement of Work EOEP-GSE-EOAD-SW-04-0001. The objective of this report is to document the complete use and life-cycle and impact of products and services delivered to a two end-user organisations, with common application goals, over a fixed period of time (Phase 2: November 2006-November 2007).

GLOSSARY

HAB	Harmful Algae Bloom
ESA	European Space Agency
NERSC	Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center
NIERSC	Nansen International Environmental and Remote Sensing Center
Sentinel-3	Future ESA mission for operational oceanographic monitoring
SLA	Service Level Agreement
WQ	Water Quality

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Service Utilisation

Seafood is the third largest export industry in Norway – after oil and gas, and metal industry – fisheries and aquaculture accounts for 5% of the national export (2006 figure). Aquaculture is an important business in our rural coastal areas. Totally 2693 licences for fish and shellfish aquaculture were open in 2006. The natural occurrence of harmful algae bloom events is a treat that causes significant losses to the aquaculture industry and is of major concern to the authorities. For Norway it is essential to have an efficient early warning and monitoring system in order to implement mitigation actions and saving values and environment.

The MarCoast Service “**Water quality monitoring of the North Sea, Kattegat and Skagerrak**” is based on precursor services developed and operated since 1998 for “the extended Norwegian” coastal waters. The core service area is limited by latitude; 66°N to 51°N and longitude; 4°W to 14°E, i.e. an extended North Sea, from 2007 covering the entire Norwegian Coastal waters (see Figure 1)¹. These precursor service activities have been funded under several projects funded by ESA, EU, Norwegian Space Centre (SatOcean program) and the Research Council of Norway. The service delivered under MarCoast has undergone a major review and upgrade from the precursor service, particularly with respect to the reliability and regularity of the service delivery. The precursor service was based on SeaWiFS and AVHRR satellite data, while the MarCoast service utilizes MERIS and MODIS EO data sources. The design, product contents and processing routines currently used have therefore undergone major improvements during the MarCoast service implementation and operations in both Phase 1 and 2.

¹ Several geographical areas of coverage have been introduced later, e.g. “Northern Europe”, “Arctic – Kara Sea”, “Laptev Sea” and “Central American Waters - Caribbean and Pacific Oceans”.

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During MarCoast Phase 1 and 2 the Norwegian Harmful Algae Bloom service has been developed and operated with two formal SLA users - the **Norwegian Directorate for Fisheries (FD)** and the **Norwegian Seafood Federation (FLH)**. The public access to the dissemination web-site of the service has also opened for service access to several other public and private users from Norway, Denmark, Sweden and UK. Regular use of the service products has also been implemented in cooperation with **Norwegian Institute for Water Research (NIVA)** and the meteorological service **met.no**. FerryBox data from three vessels have been made available from NIVA for use by the service and its validation. The service is coordinated with the national priorities under the Norwegian Space Centre's SatOcean Programme.

The geographical coverage of the service has expanded from covering the "southern Norwegian coastal / North Sea" waters to cover the entire Norwegian coastal waters as well as the North Sea and Barents Sea.

The satellite EO data portfolio, includes both standard ESA MERIS water quality parameters and regionally tuned algorithms for retrieval of the chlorophyll-*a*, sediments and yellow substance distribution. Sea surface temperature (SST) information is also provided. met.no now also provides regular model forecasting of the phytoplankton distribution for the southern coastal Norwegian waters, which are used in case of identified HAB events of concern to the aquaculture authorities or industry.

The MarCoast HAB service concept has been "re-used" for other regions and is now implemented for operation for the Central American Waters under the ESA DUE "DIVERSITY project". The concept is also implemented under other project activities for the Kara and Laptev Seas and soon also for the Caspian Sea.

TARGET SLA AND OTHER USERS

The Norwegian HAB monitoring and forecasting service has two Service Level Agreement (SLA) end-user-organizations covering one Legally mandated organization:

- The Norwegian Fisheries Directorate (**FD**)

and one industrial user –federating body:

- Norwegian Seafood Federation (**FHL** - Fiskeri- og Havbruksnæringens Landsforening)

FD: The national authority responsible for the implementation of and monitoring of Norwegian fisheries regulations, including information concerning HAB events in relation to the aquaculture industry. With respect to monitoring of HAB in Norwegian waters a contingency plan for emergency situations in Norwegian Coastal waters are in place and a web-based emergency portal is under implementation. FD provides guidance and regulations to the aquaculture industry in case of HAB events in Norwegian coastal waters. A link with the latest published satellite image from the MarCoast service provided through the "Emergency portal for the coastal waters" of the Directorate, as well as through the national information site for the Norwegian Ministry of Fisheries. A statement from FD (Gunnar Larsen) on the MarCoast service performance during Phase 2 is quoted in the following sections.

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FHL represents the majority of companies within the Norwegian fisheries sector. It is associated with the Confederation of Norwegian Business and Industry, which is the main organization for Norwegian employers in manufacturing industries, services and crafts. FHL represents the interests of more than 500 member companies with about 8000 employees. A statement from FHL (Kjell Maroni) on the MarCoast service performance during Phase 2 is quoted in the following sections.

Daily updated satellite data (image files) from the MarCoast NERSC service are regularly provided for further use and dissemination to the **Norwegian Institute for water Research (NIVA)** and the **Norwegian Meteorological Service - met.no**. A letter stating met.no's use of the MarCoast service is attached in the Annex.

By making the service (@ <http://HAB.nersc.no>) available in the public domain, the service has obtained a range of institutional and individual regular users. Some of these are known - including the **Trondhjem Biological Station, University of Trondheim** and **SINTEF Aquaculture and Fisheries (letter and example report enclosed in ANNEX)**.

SERVICE DISSEMINATION

The core dissemination is done through the NERSC MarCoast service web site <http://HAB.nersc.no>. The Norwegian Directorate for Fisheries, also disseminate the MarCoast information products through a link at their own national emergency portal (http://www.fiskeridir.no/fiskeridir/fiskeridirektoratets_beredskapsportal), where they have established a dedicated http-link to access our most recent MarCoast service EO data products.

The Norwegian Ministry of Fisheries also utilize the MarCoast service data on their own national fisheries portal (http://www.fisheries.no/aquaculture/environment/environment_pollution/).

The Norwegian Seafood Federation (FHL) provides a link to the MarCoast service from their home page at <http://www.fhl.no/>.

An ftp-link is also established for transfer of various GeoTIFF image products to Norwegian Institute for Waters Research (NIVA) and for use in the Norwegian Space Centre/NIVA SatOcean portal <http://otra.niva.no/sathav/>.

Also the Norwegian Meteorological service met.no have access to (delivered via ftp) and disseminates the service data products through their web map server <http://wms.met.no/moncoze/> (Figure 2).

The NERSC MarCoast service approach has been partly implemented for the Central American Waters (under the ESA DUE DIVERSITY project). The MarCoast service and the Mesoamerican service were presented with a paper - "*Integrated monitoring and forecasting of algae blooms in Norwegian and Mesoamerican Coastal Waters*" - at the 32nd International Symposium for Remote Sensing of the Environment (ISRSE), San Jose, Costa Rica, June 2007.

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Figure 2: An example of a MarCoast service satellite detected algae blooms (left) and modelled phytoplankton (right) in coastal waters on March 27th 2007. Model data from <http://wms.met.no/moncoze>

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assessment of impact and benefit

The EO based information products is for our users one of several sources of information about the marine environment and harmful algae blooms in particular. The availability of all the different information sources and their integration is accordingly important for the quality of the overall assessment and utilization.

The satellite EO data provides in this respect unique spatial information in particular for the coastal waters off-shore, where *in situ* sampling is much more scarce in both the time and space domains.

Marine ecosystem modelling is “still immature” and this type of satellite EO product is useful for the validation of the model quality and capabilities (see letter from met.no in ANNEX).

Regularly, field monitoring programs typical operates with a once per week up-date during normal operations and the EO based service provides up to daily updates of information products. The increased frequency can be critical in early detection of changes in the environmental conditions and accordingly initiate needed actions at an earlier stage.

Complementarily of the information sources is a key word in this respect and the following quote is received from the Directorate of Fisheries (Gunnar Larsen, Senior Adviser): *“The information we (FD) receive through MarCoast is an important basis for our contingency/monitoring with regard to harmful and toxic phytoplankton. Together with information from (ocean) circulation models, meteorological data and field investigations this forms a very good and useful tool in order to alert the aquaculture industry and necessary mitigation actions can be implemented in a short term and longer term perspectives.”*

.. and the Norwegian Seafood Federation (Kjell Maroni, Director R&D) commented in this respect: *“The HAB service from MarCoast has been integrated in our (Norwegian Seafood Federeartion - FHL) web-site for the last years, and we get different comments from the fishfarmers about it. Most of the comments are positive, but a few also see the service as something they get from other sources. What they do not consider then is that the service they get from other sources also build on information / service from MarCoast.”*

SINTEF Fisheries and Aquaculture (Karl Tangen, senior scientist) express in their letter included in the ANNEX: *“SINTEF Fisheries and Aquaculture is running an operational monitoring and forecasting service for insurance companies and their aquaculture clients in Norway. The service is primarily aiming at fish farms and their reduction of potential losses due to unfavourable environmental conditions.*

1. *During 2007 the MarCoast HAB information has been of particular value during cases when harmful phytoplankton species have been detected and documented near the coast upstream Norway. Enclosed please see some examples of weekly reports during such cases:*

1. *Chlorophyll distribution during a bloom of Verrucophora and Chrysochromulina associated with fish kills in Danish waters in March-April with a risk for spreading to the Norwegian coast by the Baltic Current and the Norwegian Coastal Current.*

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2. *Chlorophyll distribution after detection of *Karenia mikimotoi* (toxic to fish) in September in the Skagerrak area with the risk of a massive bloom and spreading to fish farms.*
3. *Detection of high chlorophyll concentrations offshore in Skagerrak in July, without knowing whether this was a bloom of an harmful species."*

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critical analysis of utility for end-user organization

The data provide by the NERSC MarCoast service is assessed daily by its users, during the main algae growth season, through the web-access the updated information products. The value of the service is first full materialized when a harmful algae bloom is early detected and that actions can be implemented according to contingency plan of the authorities and by the industry itself. During the regular monitoring mode the direct benefit is less visible, however a continuous monitoring is required by the authorities and expected by the industry.

Since the monitoring is based on the use of several sources and suppliers of data and information, a system full integration "all" information components would have been desirable. This is a longer-term goal to implement that can be done through the use of distributed web-map technologies, and a pilot system is under development in the FP6 IST InterRisk project coordinated by NERSC. Technical, managerial and practical constraints need to be considered and agreed, including commercial proprietary rights for access to data from various sources.

In this respect the following statement is received from the Directorate of Fisheries: *"Information from MarCoast together with other sources such as FerryBox and field data from national, Swedish and Danish programmes is a part of the daily routines and a part of our internal contingency plan.*

During the bloom of Pymnesium parvum between august and September in Ryfylke/Rogaland (the fjords north east of Stavanger) 135 tons of salmon died. The bloom and the spatial extent of this algae (specie) was locally confined to narrow fjords and with a low biomass, however if the bloom had spread to the waters masses outside this could have cause larges losses to the Norwegian aquaculture business. Information from NERSC/MarCoast was consequently important in order to monitor the changes in the area outside the expected influence area."

.. and the Norwegian Seafood Federation commented in this respect: *"As the last year has been a year with no dramatic episodes with harmful algal blooms, the service hasn't really been "tested". If a situation with HAB's detectable from satellite directly or indirectly we are sure the service will prove its value."*

SINTEF Fisheries and Aquaculture express further in their letter: *"The HAB information provided by ESA GMES MarCoast by NERSC is extensively used and is now part of our standard information sources. Since the presentations are updated on a daily basis they are important for our operational assessments of the distribution and dynamics of algal biomass and are the only source at present for information offshore in Kattegat, Skagerrak, the North Sea and the Norwegian Sea. We frequently refer to this information in our standard weekly report to the fish farmers."* One example report (in Norwegian) is included in the ANNEX.

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comparison with alternative services and information sources

The nine years “history” (since 1998) of the NERSC WQ service for Norwegian waters implies the build up of a strong relation and confidence between the users and the provider. Together the technical skill in producing the information products, their presentation and dissemination as well as the regional knowledge in order to produce the correct assessment of the state of the environment, are essential for the performance of the service. Availability of a regionally tuned and validated retrieval algorithm is “unique”, however the routine processing and disseminations tools are more general and not “unique” to the service.

The service has implemented and routinely generates and delivers data products in the Google Earth (KML format - Figure 1), however the function has not been extensively promoted or used. Further developments for Google applications will allow for integration of the service data products with other information/data provided in KML. Google is also commonly used for display, which may add on to promote the service, however it operates in the public domain and have also limited capabilities wrt. export of data for own further processing.

The complementarities and integrated use of the different information sources (all are needed) is essential for the quality of the overall service delivery.

The following statement is received from the Directorate of Fisheries: *“There is no alternative to this important information only supplements in the form of filed observations that mainly covers the near coastal waters and fjords. Ferrybox is a source that are used to monitor (algae) populations in open (ocean) waters, but provide only limited information.”*

.. and the Norwegian Seafood Federation commented in this respect: *“We have also been "experimenting" a little the last year to combine MarCoast information with the register of sites in use for aquaculture in Norway, with wind data / forecast from the Meteorological Institute in Norway and combining these data into Google Earth based maps. This looks promising, and we are in the process of searching for student help to develop and improve this as a service freely available on our website. If this succeed the use of the MarCoast data will be improved we think.”*

2. SINTEF Fisheries and Aquaculture concludes their letter with: *“There have repeatedly been observations of massive blooms in the Norwegian Sea, detected from the HAB satellite images, causing alerts along the northern coast since the blooms might be potential harmful phytoplankton. On most occasions such blooms have been harmless but the fish farmers have expressed that they want information as early as possible, which give time to prepare countermeasures. On other occasions toxic Chrysochromulina blooms (e.g. in 1988 and 1991) have occurred at unexpected times and places in south and north Norway and caused massive fish kills. It is our belief that an operational satellite remote sensing service at that time may have reduced the losses by providing early information to the environmental forecasting service for fish farms.”*

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RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

The regular operations as planned and agreed in the SLAs are sufficient for the service, however lack of or delays in provision of updated EO based information products is an issue. Particularly when such delays occur during critical bloom periods (as the have had a tendency to do!). It is important that prepared or known delay in or lack of data is communicated to the users as early as possible. Some complaints have been received from users in this respect. A user comments to this is given the value statement from FD and FHL quoted in Section 0.

“A tool and service with a complete integration” of “all” available information sources about the marine environment is a desirable way forward for future service improvements. Development along this line is one of the core issues and challenges of the GMES implementation. For this service we will improve our capabilities exploiting development done in other research projects such as InterRisk (see Section 0). Also expanding the Goolge Earth function/capabilities of the service is a direction that should be investigated. See users comments quoted in Section 0:

The initiation of the future ESA Sentinel-3 mission (with MERIS follow-on sensor) is important in order to maintain the users confidence in a long-term sustainability of the service, also beyond the lifetime of the current missions.

3. SINTEF Fisheries and Aquaculture recommend further in their letter: *“In full operation the system has used a combined set of information to monitor HABs.*
 1. *Samples collected along the coast (ca. 50 locations on weekly basis) and continuously analysed for species composition and concentrations*
 2. *Automatic measurements with a set of sensors (chlorophyll, light beam attenuation, nutrients and many others) on buoys on 4-6 locations in the Norwegian coastal current (not in operation at present) with true time transmission of data*
 3. *Satellite remote sensing products have been used to the extent they have been available in near true time.”*

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Conclusion

The utility of the MarCoast “**Water quality monitoring of the North Sea, Kattegat and Skagerrak**” Service provided by Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center has been assessed by our SLA users. The following value statements are in this respect presented as a conclusion for Phase 2 utility:

User value statement FD:

“The Directorate of Fisheries is a daily user of <http://HAB.nersc.no> services delivered from the Nansen Remote Sensing Centre. Under HAB's events this services is special important for our work – water sampling and information. We are very pleased with the SLA agreement so far.”

Gunnar Larsen, FD - 9th May 2007

User value statement FHL:

“In basic the Norwegian Seafood Federation (FHL) see the <http://HAB.nersc.no> service to be in line with the SLA agreement with the Nansen Remote Sensing Centre, although the server stability has been a bit unregular the last months, but also appreciate that this kind of problems will occur in periods for most web-/ITI-based services. We are not sure how many of our members is using the service on a day-to-day-basis, but know that members in areas of Norway where HAB's are most probable to occur are aware of the service, and will be using it when/if blooms of potential problem is coming. The service functions very well in cooperation with the national algal web-page.”

Kjell Maroni, FHL – 8th May 2007

.. and from two non-SLA users:

SINTEF Aquaculture and Fisheries, Trondheim:

“We are continuously monitoring your service and find the satellite images useful and a quite high correlation with our in situ observations, at least during high pressure situations with little cloud cover”.

Leading scientist Dr. Karl Tangen – 27th March, 2007

Trondheim Biological station, University of Trondheim:

“The operational remote sensing of phytoplankton blooms, coloured dissolved organic matter and total suspended matter along the Norwegian coast from HAB-NERSC is of outmost importance for harmful algae monitoring in Norway/Scandinavia. The data provided, also implemented also in Google Earth, is the current state-of-the-art for governmental decision making, general monitoring, understanding of plankton and water mass dynamics for both applied and basic science. Together with the Norwegian observation network, providing water samples for HAB species and the Norwegian food authority (Mattilsynet) providing phytoplankton toxicity tests in mussels along the Norwegian coast line, the NERSC-HAB monitoring service is world leading in operational phytoplankton monitoring. Internationally, HAB monitoring is hot topic and NERSC (Lasse Pettersson) was asked to write a chapter in

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the new 3rd edition of the highly known and used UNESCO-book "Pigments in Oceanography". At present, the international editorial committee of the book (Roy, Johnsen, Egeland, Llewellyn and Wright) regard NERSC among the world leaders of operational remote sensing of phytoplankton blooms."

Prof. Geir Johnsen – 20th April, 2007

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Norwegian
Meteorological Institute
met.no

Our Ref:
Our Date:
17 October 2007

Your Ref:
Your Date

Lasse Pettersson
NERSC
Thormøhlensgate 47
N-5006 Bergen
Norway

Satellite algae observations in met.no's operational forecasting

Dear Lasse,

As you know, we at met.no have been hosting a website (<http://moncoze.met.no>) for displaying marine environmental information for the southern Norwegian coast. The site started as a project activity in the MONCOZE project in 2002 and has run continuously since then, with a couple of upgrades. The project site has been discontinued after the termination of the MONCOZE project, but the web service has continued, now as a web mapping service (WMS) located at <http://wms.met.no/moncoze>.

A primary focus of this activity is to supply useful information on the state of the marine ecosystem to national authorities and coastal managers. One component of this is the operational numerical forecasting service for nutrients and algae we carry out in cooperation with the Institute of Marine Research (IMR). Another component is the daily updated ocean color and algae concentration imagery that NERSC has supplied for several years. We view these observations as essential information in a monitoring and forecasting system for harmful algal blooms. Marine ecosystem models are still immature for forecasting purposes, so it is extremely valuable to have access to such data for validation of the model. The two figures on the attached page show how we can use the satellite image to check the performance of the model. One of our planned activities for 2007-2008 is implementation of the satellite chlorophyll-a data in our operational validation system.

We look forward to continued collaboration on marine ecosystem monitoring and forecasting.

Sincerely yours,

Bruce Hackert
Senior Scientist

Postal address: Office
P.O. Box 43, Blindern Gaustadveien 303
NO-0313 OSLO, Norway

Telephone: +47 22 96 30 00
Telefax: +47 22 96 30 50
e-mail: met@met.no
Internet: met.no

Bank account: 7694 05 06628
Swift code: DNLANO2K

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Figure: Two screen shots from the WMS client at <http://wms.met.no/moncoze> showing (left) a MERIS chl-a image supplied by NERSC and (right) a forecast field for diatoms from the met.no/IMR coupled hydrodynamic-biological model. Both pictures valid for 1 October 2007 12 UTC. This comparison is used for validation of the model prognosis, noting that the model approximates some observed features while missing others.

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Lasse Petterson
NERSC
Thornøhlensgt 47
S006 Bergen

**SINTEF Fisheries and
Aquaculture**
Marine Resources Technology

Address: NO-7465 Trondheim, Norway
Location:
SINTEF Sealab
Brattøraia 17B

Telephone: +47 4000 5350
Fax: +47 932 70 701

E-mail: fish@sintef.no
Internet: www.sintef.no

Enterprise No.:
NO 980 478 270 MVA

Your ref.:
LP

Our ref.:
KTE181007

Direct line:

Trondheim,
2007-10-19

Our use of ESA MarCoast products provided by NERSC

SINTEF Fisheries and Aquaculture is running an operational monitoring and forecasting service for insurance companies and their aquaculture clients in Norway. The service is primarily aiming at fish farms and their reduction of potential losses due to unfavourable environmental conditions. It was developed as an application of the EUREKA/EUROMAR project SEAWATCH and started its operations in 1987 (MARINET) and has been in continuous operation since then by OCEANOR and SINTEF Fisheries and Aquaculture. The primary motivation was harmful algal blooms (HAB) that caused mortality and economic losses in salmon farms on the south and west coast in 1981 and repeatedly afterwards but is later extended to forecasting of harmful jellyfish invasions, acute pollution including oilspills, and extreme weather and sea state conditions.

In full operation the system has used a combined set of information to monitor HABs.

1. Samples collected along the coast (ca. 50 locations on weekly basis) and continuously analysed for species composition and concentrations
2. Automatic measurements with a set of sensors (chlorophyll, light beam attenuation, nutrients and many others) on buoys on 4-6 locations in the Norwegian coastal current (not in operation at present) with true time transmission of data
3. Satellite remote sensing products have been used to the extent they have been available in near true time.

The HAB information provided by ESA GMES MarCoast by NERSC is extensively used and is now part of our standard information sources. Since the presentations are updated on a daily basis they are important for our operational assessments of the distribution and dynamics of algal biomass and are the only source at present for information offshore in Kartegat, Skagerrak, the North Sea and the Norwegian Sea. We frequently refer to this information in our standard weekly report to the fish farmers.

During 2007 the MarCoast HAB information has been of particular value during cases when harmful phytoplankton species have been detected and documented near the coast upstream Norway. Enclosed please see some examples of weekly reports during such cases:

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1. Chlorophyll distribution during a bloom of *Perrucophora* and *Chrysochromulina* associated with fish kills in Danish waters in March-April with a risk for spreading to the Norwegian coast by the Baltic Current and the Norwegian Coastal Current.
2. Chlorophyll distribution after detection of *Karenia mikimotoi* (toxic to fish) in September in the Skagerrak area with the risk of a massive bloom and spreading to fish farms.
3. Detection of high chlorophyll concentrations offshore in Skagerrak in July, without knowing whether this was a bloom of an harmful species.

There have repeatedly been observations of massive blooms in the Norwegian Sea, detected from the HAB satellite images, causing alerts along the northern coast since the blooms might be potential harmful phytoplankton. On most occasions such blooms have been harmless but the fish farmers have expressed that they want information as early as possible, which give time to prepare countermeasures. On other occasions toxic *Chrysochromulina* blooms (e.g. in 1988 and 1991) have occurred at unexpected times and places in south and north Norway and caused massive fish kills. It is our belief that an operational satellite remote sensing service at that time may have reduced the losses by providing early information to the environmental forecasting service for fish farms.

Yours sincerely

Karl Tangen
Senior Scientist
SINTEF Fisheries and Aquaculture
Marine Resources Technology

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GJENSIDIGE

2007

MILJØVARSEL utarbeidet av SINTEF Fiskeri og havbruk

SITUASJONSBEKRIVELSE UKE 14-2007

SPESIALVARSEL

Det er ikke sendt ut spesialvarsel denne uken.

GENERELT

Vi har bare et fåtall nye prøver siden siste ukerapport, men de dataene vi har indikerer at våroppblomstringen utvikler seg videre med spredning inn i Finnmark. Det er ellers en fase av vårbloomingen nærmest over all, men relativt lite alger i ytre strøk i Trøndelag. Det er fortsatt kiselalger (*Skeletonema*, *Chaetoceros*, *Thalassiosira*, *Pseudo-nitzschia*, *Fragilariopsis* o.a.) som dominerer langs hele kysten med noe gelealger (*Phaeocystis*) fra Midt-Norge og nordover og mest i Troms. Det er en god del åte (mest hoppekreps) i noen prøver og mye blåskjellarver. Det begynner nå å komme småmaneter i noen håvtrekkprøver fra Midt-Norge. **Verrucophora (nytt navn for Chattonella) observeres på Vestlandet. Chaetoceros convolutus er sett med kraftig utviklede pigger, mest i Nord-Trøndelag. I Danmark er det en svært kraftig oppblomstring av Verrucophora og Chrysochromulina, som gjør at fisk (regnbueørret) ikke kan settes i sjøen nå.**

LOKALT

Nord-Norge (område 9-12): Oppblomstringen har bredt seg nordover, med store bestander av kiselalger noen steder, stort sett de samme artene som sørpå. **Alexandrium tamarense** (og *A. ostenfeldii*) registreres flere steder, mest i Troms der vi hadde tyngdepunktet av fjorårets oppblomstring i juli – august.

Midt-Norge (område 6-8): Våroppblomstringen fortsetter med dominans av kiselalger (*Skeletonema*, *Pseudo-nitzschia*, *Chaetoceros socialis*) og små innslag av gelealger (*Phaeocystis*). **Chaetoceros convolutus** og *C. borealis* (skadelig for fisk) finnes i håvtrekkprøver fra hele området. **Det påvises en del Alexandrium tamarense flere steder.**

Vestlandet (område 3-5): Våroppblomstringen, som er dominert av kiselalger, er på retur i flere fjordstrøk på Vestlandet, men er fortsatt ganske kraftig enkelte steder. Helt i sør er det en massiv oppblomstring av kiselalger (*Skeletonema* o.a.). Ingen nye opplysninger om dødelighet.

Skagerrak-kysten (område 1-2): Algeforekomstene er store i hele området, og det observeres misfarget sjø, med *Skeletonema* som dominerende art. **Vi minner om at det tidligere har vært blomstringsmengder av Verrucophora (=Chattonella aff. verruculosa) i perioden februar – mai i dette området.**

KONTAKTNETTET

Det rapporteres fremdeles om høye sjøtemperaturer og ellers normale i forhold for årstiden.

VARSEL FOR UKE 15-2007

VURDERING AV SITUASJONEN

Alger: Våroppblomstringen vil fortsette i nord, men etter hvert avta sør for Trøndelag. Sannsynligvis blir det fortsatt dominans av kiselalgene *Skeletonema*, *Chaetoceros*, *Pseudo-nitzschia*, *Thalassiosira* og gelealger (*Phaeocystis*) i Nord-Norge. Vi vil fremdeles følge opp med hensyn på potensielt skadelige arter, spesielt mulige tidlige oppblomstringer av *Alexandrium* og **spredning av Verrucophora fra danske områder**. Vi oppfordrer alle til å følge godt med på sikten i sjøen og fisken og at det **tas ut vannprøver til analyse ved SINTEF SeaLab ved dårlig sikt i sjøen** og tegn til problem.

Maneter og annet dyreplankton: Vi begynner å finne småmaneter i algeprøvene og **ber om at alle observasjoner av maneter meldes inn til SINTEF SeaLab**. Vi anbefaler fortsatt årvåkenhet for **småmaneter, ribbemaneter og brennmaneter** langs hele kysten.

Vær: Meteorologisk Institutt (MI) varsler **nordvest liten storm i Trøndelag og Nordland torsdag** og ellers mye kuling langs kysten i langtidsperioden. **Vi er fortsatt i en årstid med ustabil vær og minner om at det kan bli sterkere vind enn varslet og at langtidsvarslene er usikre.**

Sjøtemperatur: Sjøtemperaturene har snudd til svak økning i Kyststrømmen i Skagerrak og langs kysten forøvrig, og vil holde seg høye for årstiden, spesielt i baltisk/Østersjøvann som går over i Kyststrømmen

Generelle råd: Ved redusert sikt (<4 m), misfarget sjø, ekstreme sjøtemperaturer eller endret atferd bør foring reduseres eller stoppes.

Kontakt alltid SINTEF Fiskeri og havbruk ved endret atferd eller dårlig sikt i sjøen (<4 m) for avtale om prøveinnsendelse.

Analysene er gratis for kunder av Gjensidige og if...

BEREDSKAPSGRAD

Område: 1-4 B-C Fase av våroppblomstringen, **Verrucophora**
5-12 B Våroppblomstringen under utvikling, forekomster av *Alexandrium*.
Maneter. *Chaetoceros convolutus*.

NAVN	KONTROLLERT AV	DATO
Karl Tangen		03.04.07

Beredskapsvakt i helgen: Karl Tangen (98 22 24 76)

Beredskapsvakt i uke 15/07: 1600 – 0800 Johanne Arff (98 22 24 77)

Vakttilf: 90 60 43 55

Fargeskalaen viser algemengdene (klorofyll) fra rødt (mye) til grønt og gult (ganske mye) og turkis (moderate mengder) til blått som er lite alger.

Merk store algemengder sør i Kattegat, spesielt Storebæltområdet. Det er *Verrucophora/Chattonella* i mender på opptil 15 mill/L og *Chrysochromulina* opptil 26 mill/L den siste uken. Dette er mengder som normalt gir akutt dødelighet i oppdrettsanlegg. Det er usikkert om denne oppblomstringen får en utløper til norske farvann, og vi vil følge med i utviklingen framover.

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GJENSIDIGE

2007

MILJØVARSEL utarbeidet av SINTEF Fiskeri og havbruk

Side 3

DEFINISJON AV BEREDSKAPSGRADER:

- A. Normalsituasjon
- B. Forberedende beredskap (Vurderingsfase):
Melding om trussel foreligger. Økt aktsomhet
- C. Enkel beredskap (planleggingsfase):
Trussel foreligger, men er langt unna i tid, det er uklart om sonen blir berørt eller trusselen er til stede, men er ikke av alvorlig art. Føring og utsetting av smolt vurderes spesielt.
- D. Forsterket beredskap (Mobilisering):
Stor sannsynlighet for at sonen blir berørt av trussel, eller trussel som er tilstede er under utvikling. Ingen føring. Ikke utsett av settelisk. Aksjon forberedes.
- E. Full beredskap (Aksjonsfase):
Skader er nært forestående eller skjer (f.eks. fisk dør i sonen). Aktuelle tiltak settes i verk. Ingen føring. Ikke utsett av settelisk.

SINTEF Fiskeri og havbruk AS, 7465 Trondheim
Besøksadresse: SINTEF Sealab, Brattørkaia 17B, 7010 Trondheim
Telefon: 40 00 53 50, Telefax: 93 27 07 01
fish@sintef.no, www.sintef.no

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SITUASJONSBESKRIVELSE UKE 37-2007

SPESIALVARSEL

Det er ikke sendt ut spesialvarsel denne uken.

GENERELT

Det er ingen nye opplysninger om forekomsten av *Karenia* i åpen sjø i Skagerrak, men den registreres på den svenske vestkysten og langs Sørlandskysten denne uken. Satellittbilder indikerer fortsatt at det er mye alger til havs i Skagerrak. Algeforekomstene langs kysten ellers varierer fra små celledannende ytterst på kysten til lokale oppblomstringer av kiselalger (*Skeletonema*, *Pseudo-nitzschia*, *Proboscia*, *Chaetoceros*) eller dinoflagellater (*Ceratium*, *Prorocentrum*) i fjordstrøk i Nord-Norge og på Vestlandet. Det observeres lokalt ganske mye åte (hoppekreps, linsekreps, vingenesegl/kruttåte o.a.) og småmaneter og ribbemaneter. Fortsatt en del skjellyngel, mest i Nord-Trøndelag og Nordland.

LOKALT

Nord-Norge nord (område 11-12): I Finnmark og Troms er det små algeforekomster med dominans av dinoflagellater (*Ceratium* inntil 5000/L i Nord-Troms) eller kiselalger (*Proboscia*). Det er fortsatt en del skjellyngel i dette området.

Nord-Norge sør (område 9-10): Det er dinoflagellater som dominerer i det meste av området, med blomstringsmengder av *Ceratium*-arter fra Salten og sørover, mens det fortsatt er en god del kiselalger (*Proboscia*, *Chaetoceros* o.a.) fra Vesterålen til Ofoten. Småmaneter observeres også denne uken.

Midt-Norge (område 6-8): Det er små totalbestander i området, og det er bare unntaksvis påvist større mengder av kiselalger og/eller dinoflagellater i prøvematerialet denne uken. Det observeres en del småmaneter.

Vestlandet (område 3-5): Algebildet er variert med moderate forekomster på kysten, men en del lokale oppblomstringer dominert av kiselalger (*Pseudo-nitzschia* i Nordfjord og Hardangerfjorden, *Skeletonema* i Midt-Hordaland) med celledannende inntil 8 mill/L. Sør i området er det en blanded oppblomstring av *Skeletonema* og *Chaetoceros*.

Skagerrak-kysten (område 1-2): Det registreres fortsatt små til moderate forekomster av kiselalger. *Karenia* er påvist flere steder, men utbredelsen er ikke kartlagt utenskjærs. Ribbemaneten *Mnemiopsis* observeres fremdeles langs kysten.

KONTAKTNETTET

Det rapporteres om nedsatt sikt og redusert appetitt noen steder. Årsaken kan være ribbemaneter og småmaneter.

VARSEL FOR UKE 38-2007

VURDERING AV SITUASJONEN

Alger: Algesituasjonen i sør er fortsatt åpen på grunn av lite data til havs. Risikoen er fortsatt til stede for en oppblomstring av *Karenia* på sørvestlandet. Algeoppblomstringer kan ellers oppstå lokalt, spesielt hvis det blir en periode med rolig vær og lite vindomrøring. Vi vil følge opp med hensyn på potensielt skadelige arter, spesielt *Karenia* og mulige oppblomstringer til havs som nærmer seg kysten. Vi oppfordrer alle til å følge godt med på sikten i sjøen og fisken og at det tas ut vannprøver til analyse ved SINTEF SeaLab ved dårlig sikt i sjøen, dårlig appetitt hos fisken og ved andre tegn til problem.

Maneter og annet dyreplankton: Vi ser mye småmaneter og ribbemaneter i algeprøvene og ber om at alle observasjoner av maneter meldes inn til SINTEF SeaLab. Vi anbefaler fortsatt årvåkenhet for alle slags maneter langs hele kysten.

Vær: Meteorologisk Institutt (MI) varsler om sterk nordvestlig vind fra Rogaland til Trøndelag det nærmeste døgnet, men mindre vind senere i langtidsperioden. Vi er på vei inn i en periode med en mer urolig værtype og minner om at vinden kan bli kraftigere enn det som er varslet. Vi anbefaler at fortøyninger kontrolleres og at løsøre sikres.

Sjøtemperatur: Sjøtemperaturene avtar gradvis, men kan øke litt i overflaten etter vindomrøring.

Generelle råd: Reduser foring ved redusert sikt (<4 m), misfarget sjø, ekstreme sjøtemperaturer eller endret atferd.

Kontakt alltid SINTEF Fiskeri og havbruk ved endret atferd eller dårlig sikt i sjøen (<4 m) for avtale om prøveinnsendelse.

Analysene er gratis for kunder av Gjensidige og if...

BEREDSKAPSGRAD

Område:	1-3	B-D	<i>Karenia</i> , Usikker algesituasjon. Maneter
	5-8	B	Usikker algesituasjon, maneter
	9-12	B	Moderate algeforekomster. Maneter.

NAVN	KONTROLLERT AV	DATO
Karl Tangen	Johanne Arff	14.09.07

Beredskapsvakt i helgen: Karl Tangen (98 22 24 76)
Beredskapsvakt i uke 38/07: Johanne Arff (98 22 24 77)
Vakttilf: 90 60 43 55

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Øverst: Satellittbilde som viser algeforekomstene til havs (turkis-grønt-gult-rødt) denne uken.

Midten: Manet-tentakel med mengder av stavformede brennceller – vanlig i algeprøvene for tiden. Bildet er fra Trøndelag i prøve tatt på mandag.

Nederst: Blant dyreplanktonet kan det være store mengder av slike trekanter, som er larver av mosdyr. De slår seg ned og danner et brunt belegg, bl.a. på anleggsstrukturer. Bildet er fra Salten, prøve fra mandag. [il](#)

- DEFINISJON AV BEREDSKAPSGRADER:**
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 - D. Forsterket beredskap (Mobilisering)
Stor sannsynlighet for at sonen blir berørt av trussel, eller trussel som er tilstede er under utvikling. Ingen føring. Ikke utsett av settelisk. Aksjon forberedes.
 - E. Full beredskap (Aksjonfase):
Skader er nært forestående eller skjer (f.eks. fisk dør i sonen). Aktuelle tiltak settes i verk. Ingen føring. Ikke utsett av settelisk.

SINTEF Fiskeri og havbruk AS, 7465 Trondheim
Besøksadresse: SINTEF Sealab, Brattørkaia 17B, 7010 Trondheim
Telefon: 40 00 53 50, Telefax: 93 27 07 01
fish@sintef.no, www.sintef.no

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